

Adsorption of *n*-Cetyl Pyridinium Chloride at *n*-Heptane/Water Interface

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The adsorption of long chain ionic compounds at oil/water (o/w) interface has been investigated by a number of authors using the method of lowering of interfacial tension combined with Gibbs isotherm. Cockbain¹ and Vold and Groot² have used two methods for measuring the adsorption at o/w interface. One is based on the direct estimation of adsorption by titration technique before and after dispersion of a given volume of oil in a known volume of long chain electrolyte solution of constant ionic strength and the other is based on the lowering of interfacial tension. In the experiments recorded here, the adsorbed amount of *n*-Cetyl pyridinium ion (CP_y⁺) at *n*-heptane/water interface has been estimated by the direct method. The data obtained by this method have been used to test the applicability of Freundlich³, Temkin⁴ and Langmuir⁵ isotherm.

EXPERIMENTAL

Purity of the constituents : *n*-Heptane used was of G.R. quality, E. Merck, and redistilled. Sodium chloride of the same quality, freed from surfactants by heating, was used to maintain the ionic strength at a constant value. HCl of the same quality was used for the same purpose without further purification and was found not to be contaminated with surfactants as revealed from interfacial tension measurements. In all the experiments double distilled water of specific conductance $0.57 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was used.

The long chain electrolyte CP_yCl, i.e., $\text{CH}_3-(\text{CH}_2)_{15}-\overset{+}{\text{N}} \begin{array}{l} \diagup \text{CH}-\text{CH} \\ \diagdown \text{CH}=\text{CH} \end{array} \text{CH}$, mol. wt. 340.0 was the product of L. Light and Co. It was purified by repeated recrystallisation from hot alcohol till the minimum found in the surface tension *vs.* concentration curve was removed and a continuous curve was obtained. This purified sample was analysed by the micromethod for its content of C, H and N. These were found to be 73.8, 11.0 and 4.11 per cent respectively. The calculated values are 74.11, 11.27 and 4.117 per cent respectively. The analytical data of the sample indicated that it was fairly pure. Moreover its c.m.c. (Critical micelle concentration) in aqueous solution was determined by surface tension and also by conductivity measurements. It was found to be 0.00091. The approximate value of C₁₆-amine salt quoted in the literature is 0.0008⁶.

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† *Measurement of total adsorption (x) on the emulsion globules*

The procedure is the same as that described by Ghosh and Kundu⁷. Here CP_yCl was used instead of CTAB as the stabilizing ion. Ionic strengths of 0.01 and 0.1 were maintained by NaCl only and that at 0.02 by HCl and NaCl in 1 : 1 proportion. The data are recorded in the Tables I-III.

TABLE I

Temperature = $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$; Ionic strength = 0.01

10 ml. of *n*-heptane were dispersed in 100 ml of aqueous solution of CP_yCl and NaCl.

Concn. of CP_yCl before dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Equilibrium concentration of CP_yCl after dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount (x) in gm-mol. per 1 ml. of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $X \times 10^6$
2.74	0.336	2.40
3.25	0.330	2.92
3.65	0.612	3.04
4.06	0.730	3.33
4.56	0.853	3.71
7.58	2.09	5.49
11.44	4.27	7.17
12.50	4.95	7.55

TABLE II

Temperature = $30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ Ionic strength = 0.02

5 ml. of *n*-heptane were dispersed in 100 ml of aqueous soln. of CP_yCl , NaCl and HCl.

Concn. of CP_yCl before dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Equilibrium concentration of CP_yCl after dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount (x) in gm-mol per 1 ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $X \times 10^6$
1.384	0.264	2.25
1.547	0.347	2.40
1.798	0.488	2.62
2.042	0.632	2.82
2.912	1.187	3.65
4.690	2.474	4.53
5.340	2.743	5.19
6.253	3.823	4.86
7.120	4.745	4.75
7.511	4.949	5.12

TABLE III

 Temperature = $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$; Ionic strength = 0.1

 10 ml of *n*-heptane were dispersed in 100 ml of aqueous soln. of CP_yCl and $NaCl$.

Concn. of CP_yCl before dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Equilibrium concentration of CP_yCl after dispersion in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount (x) in gm-mol per 1 ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $X \times 10^6$
3.130	0.233	2.90
3.332	0.257	3.08
3.649	0.322	3.33
3.965	0.365	3.60
4.244	0.461	3.78
4.758	0.408	4.35
5.303	1.031	4.27

Estimation of total surface area (S)

S was evaluated from the following expression $S = \frac{x}{\Gamma} \text{cm}^2$ for the ionic strength 0.01 and 0.02. Since there was present a sufficient quantity of added neutral electrolyte Γ has been calculated using the equation $\Gamma = \frac{1}{2.303 RT} \cdot \frac{d\gamma}{d \log C}$ from the lowering of interfacial tension. Intefacial tension (γ) was measured by the same method as that described by Kundu and Ghosh⁷. The values of Γ are recorded in the Tables IV and V. The values of S are recorded in the Tables VI and VII.

TABLE IV

 Temperature = $30^{\circ} \pm 0.05^{\circ}$ Ionic strength = 0.01

Concentration of CP_yCl in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Adsorbed amount (Γ) in gm-ion/cm ² of the interface (using Gibbs equ ⁿ .) $X10^{10}$
0.138	2.24
0.174	2.27
0.256	2.34
0.347	2.40
0.427	2.46
0.535	2.52
0.638	2.56
0.759	2.59
0.910	2.63
1.17	2.63

TABLE V

Temperature = $30^{\circ} \pm 0.5^{\circ}$. Ionic strength = 0.02

0.208	2.41
0.263	2.46
0.347	2.59
0.398	2.72
0.457	2.73
0.502	2.80
0.632	3.02
0.793	3.06

TABLE VI

Ionic strength = 0.01

Equilibrium concentration of CP _y Cl in gm-ion/l $C \times 10^4$	Γ from Gibbs isotherm in gm-ion/cm ² $\times 10^{10}$	Adsorbed amount in gm-ion/l ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $x_e \times 10^6$	Total surface area (<i>S</i>) in cm ² per 1 ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $S = x/\Gamma \text{ cm}^2$ $S \times 10^{-4}$	Adsorbed amount (<i>x</i>) in gm-ion/1 ml. of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed assuming $S = 1.23 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2$
0.336	2.39	2.40	—	2.92
0.330	2.39	2.92	1.22	2.92
0.612	2.56	3.04	1.19	3.14
0.730	2.59	3.33	1.29	3.18

Average value of $S = 1.23 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2$

TABLE VII

Ionic strength = 0.02

Equilibrium concentration of CP _y Cl in gm-mol/l. $C \times 10^4$	Γ from Gibbs isotherm in gm-ion/cm ² $\times 10^{10}$	Adsorbed amount (<i>x</i>) in gm-ion/1 ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $\times 10^9$	Total surface area (<i>S</i>) in cm ² per 1 ml of <i>n</i> -heptane dispersed $S \times 10^{-4}$
0.264	2.46	2.25	0.915
0.347	2.58	2.40	0.930
0.488	2.81	2.62	0.932
0.632	3.02	2.82	0.934

Average value of $S = 0.927 \times 10^4 \text{ cm}^2$.

DISCUSSION

When the volume of the oil and that of the aqueous solution are kept constant, but the concentration of the long chain electrolyte only is varied, S should remain constant provided the dispersion is effected in exactly the same way in every case. It is, however, not possible to control all the factors involved in effecting dispersion and hence S may vary slightly from emulsion to emulsion. It may be noticed from the data recorded in the Tables VI and VII that variation of S from its average value S_a is small.

The total adsorption (x) on a constant surface area S_a should be used to test the applicability of different adsorption isotherms. $x = \frac{x_e}{S} \cdot S_a$ and the value of x for the different concentrations of $CP_\nu Cl$ are recorded in column 5 of the Table VI (x_e is the total adsorption found experimentally).

According to the Freundlich³ isotherm a plot of $\log x$ against $\log C$ should be linear and this is actually the case for all the ionic strength investigated. The values of ν found are 2.41, 3.16 and 2.97 at the ionic strengths 0.01, 0.02 and 0.1 respectively. Davies and Rideal⁸ reported ν is equal to 3 for the ionic adsorption at a constant ionic strength.

Temkin⁴ isotherm is said to hold good when a plot of x against $\log C$ should be linear and the linear relationship holds over the ranges of concentration of $CP_\nu Cl$ investigated at the ionic strengths 0.1 and 0.02. At the ionic strength 0.01 the linear relationship holds within the concentration range 4.95×10^{-4} to $0.612 \times 10^{-4} M$.

According to Langmuir⁵ isotherm a plot of $1/x$ against $1/C$ should be linear when f , the activity coefficient, is constant for a constant ionic strength. It appears that this isotherm holds over the entire range of concentration of $CP_\nu Cl$ investigated at the ionic strength 0.1. At the ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.02 this isotherm holds over a limited range of concentration of $CP_\nu Cl$. As the saturation point of the interface is approached the deviation becomes more marked and the increase in adsorption of $CP_\nu Cl$ is greater than what is expected from Langmuir's isotherm. This fact may be accounted for in the following way :

The interface is neutral as a whole and so it must include the diffuse part of the electrical double layer and must possess considerable thickness. Davies has suggested that the plane passing through the centres of the ionic heads of a long chain electrolyte at o/w interface lies at a distance about 3 \AA below the oil phase in the aqueous side of the interface. According to Ghosh^{9,10} this view may be correct when the ionic strength of the solution is high, say, above 0.1. When the ionic strength is low, say 0.01 the thickness of the electrical double layer will be of the order of 31 \AA^2 and the charged heads of the adsorbed long chain ions are likely to be at different distances appreciably greater than 3 \AA from the oil phase.

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As the saturation point of the interface is approached at low ionic strengths, the Van der Waal type of attraction exerted jointly by the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups of the long chain and $=\text{CH}$ groups of the pyridine nucleus of CP_y^+ lying in the aqueous side of the interface may overcome the electrostatic repulsion due to the charged heads and may lead to adsorption greater than what should follow from Langmuir isotherm.

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